

Local Government in Austria

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Austria: An Introduction

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The responsibility of providing public services in most areas, such as education, health, elderly care or transport, is shared among all three levels of government. The intertwinement of public service provision and financial flows, however, is often considered complex. For a long time, a more transparent distribution of competences between all levels of government as well as organizational and financial disentanglement of public service provision is being discussed. Nevertheless, these reforms are only being implemented reluctantly, due to given constitutional federal structures.^{100 101}

Coordination Between the National Government and the *Länder*

When jointly providing public services the need for coordination and coherent actions between levels of government is considerable. Traditionally, the allocation of responsibilities is specified in agreements under private law or in the framework of simple legal regulations. To meet centralistic requirements and decentral preferences, the Constitution (Article 15(a))¹⁰² provides the possibility for the national government and the *Länder* governments to enter into agreements on specified policy fields, for example in health policy¹⁰³ or elementary education.¹⁰⁴

¹⁰⁰ An OECD study categorizes Austria as a state with centralized fiscal structures, which ‘tends to combine low autonomy and responsibility with a high level of co-determination and strong fiscal rules and frameworks’ for subnational governments. See Hansjörg Blöchliger and Jaroslaw Kantorowicz, ‘Fiscal Constitutions: An Empirical Assessment’ (2015) 1248 OECD Economics Department Working Papers <<https://doi.org/10.1787/5jrjctrxp8ren>> 5.

¹⁰¹ See Helfried Bauer and Peter Biwald, ‘Governance im österreichischen Bundesstaat voranbringen’ in Helfried Bauer, Peter Biwald and Karoline Mitterer (eds), *Governance-Perspektiven in Österreichs Föderalismus. Herausforderungen und Optionen* (NWV 2019); Erich Thöni and Helfried Bauer, ‘Föderalismusreformen oder Gamsbartföderalismus in Österreich?’ in Peter Biwald and others (eds) *Nachhaltig wirken. Impulse für den öffentlichen Sektor* (NWV 2019).

¹⁰² Art 15(a) agreements are guaranteed by the Constitution and were made possible in 2004 through a constitutional reform.

¹⁰³ Federal Ministry of Finance, ‘Zielsteuerung Gesundheit’ <<https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/budget/finanzbeziehungen-laender-gemeinden/paktum-finanzausgleich-ab-2017.html>> accessed 21 February 2020.

¹⁰⁴ Agreement on Elementary Education for the Years 2018/19 to 2021/22, BGBl. I no 103/2018.

Coordination Between all Three Levels of Government

Another example is the Pact on the Fiscal Equalization,¹⁰⁵ which is agreed upon between national government, *Länder* and municipalities for a time period of four to six years. In this pact the financial flows between the levels of government are settled. This affects among other tasks the rights of taxation, the distribution of revenues from the shared federal taxes and who bears specific costs. The Pact on the Fiscal Equalization has proven to be a central element for securing the financial autonomy of all government levels, due to the fact that all stakeholders have to agree to the pact. In this process the local level also has a strong role and is represented by the two local government associations (LGAs), the Austrian Association of Municipalities (*Österreichischer Gemeindebund*) for smaller rural municipalities, and the Austrian Association of Cities and Towns (*Österreichischer Städtebund*), for middle-sized to larger cities. Ideally both associations have a joint position during the negotiations with the national and *Länder*-level. However, there are topics where a balance of interests for all sizes of municipalities is not sufficiently met, which weakens the negotiation position of the local level as a whole in this process.

Coordination Between *Länder* and Municipalities

Diverse intergovernmental relationships exist between the *Länder* and their respective municipalities. These include *Länder*-specific regulations for providing and financing public services, complex financial transfers, deployment of human resources for different services and organizational regulations. Regulation for cooperation strategies and instruments between the two levels are not common. The 2018 Regional Development Act of the *Land* of Styria¹⁰⁶ is however a recent attempt for a strategic orientation regarding regional development between the *Land*, the Styrian regions and their municipalities. Furthermore, the act stipulates tasks, instruments as well as joint distribution of resources for the development of regions.¹⁰⁷ Other examples relate to reforms enforcing more cooperation on subnational level through outsourcing of organizational units as independent legal entities, regional funds, or the establishment of funds for joint service provision and financing like hospital districts in some *Länder* or the social fund in the *Land* of Vorarlberg.¹⁰⁸

The potential trade-off between cooperation and supervision is especially relevant for municipalities and their respective *Länder*, as the *Länder* governments are responsible for municipal supervision regarding local finances. Recent developments show that the *Länder* do not predominantly exercise control through this role, but strongly see themselves in a

¹⁰⁵ Federal Ministry of Finance, 'Paktum zum Finanzausgleich 2017'

<<https://www.bmf.gv.at/themen/budget/finanzbeziehungen-laender-gemeinden/paktum-finanzausgleich-ab-2017.html>> accessed 21 February 2020.

¹⁰⁶ Styrian Spatial and Regional Development Act (Steiermärkisches Landes- und Regionalentwicklungsgesetz), LGBL. no 117/2017.

¹⁰⁷ Bauer and Biwald, 'Governance im österreichischen Bundesstaat voranbringen', above.

¹⁰⁸ *ibid.*

consulting position as well. *Länder* can also influence investments and infrastructure projects of the local level, as they manage cost contributions, financial transfers and grants for such ventures. This poses a discrepancy to the constitutional right to self-government of the municipalities, which is partly limited through the previously stated operational and financial intertwinement with the *Länder*. Therefore, there are calls for reducing these interdependencies.

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

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Thöni E and Bauer H, 'Föderalismusreformen oder Gamsbartföderalismus in Österreich?' in Peter Biwald and others (eds) *Nachhaltig wirken. Impulse für den öffentlichen Sektor* (NWV 2019)

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